

FACTORS OF DEVELOPING THE 1ST RHYTHM PERCEPTION IN MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS: METHODS OF DETERMINATION BASED ON PRIORITY FOR MULTISENSORY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the factors influencing the development of the ability to perceive rhythm 1 in music education students. Special attention is paid to multisensory educational approaches, studying the role of the joint activation of visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile sensations in the formation of rhythmic skills. The article considers methods for identifying factors in the process of developing the 1st rhythm perception through various pedagogical methods and diagnostic tools. It is emphasized that approaches based on multisensory education contribute to a deeper understanding and mastery of rhythm, which serves to increase the effectiveness of music education.

Introduction. Rhythm is one of the main and most important elements in music education. In particular, rhythm 1, that is, a rhythmic structure in a simple unit, serves as a foundation for a deep understanding and performance of musical processes. Students' correct perception and control of rhythm 1 plays an important role in the development of their musical skills. In recent years, the multisensory educational approach has gained great attention in music education. This approach, combining visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile sensations, helps students effectively master musical knowledge. This article analyzes the factors that contribute to the development of rhythm 1 among students of the music education department and considers methods for identifying them based on prioritizing multisensory education.

1. Rhythm and its importance in education. Rhythm is a rhythmic sequence of musical works based on time units, which provides the movement, flow and expression of music. In music education, a deep sense of rhythm is important in developing the creative and technical skills of a musician. Rhythm 1, or rhythm in a simple unit, is the simplest and most common rhythmic unit, which is accepted as the basis in many musical genres. By mastering this rhythm, students create a solid foundation for understanding and performing complex rhythmic patterns.

2. The main factors in the development of the sense of rhythm. The sense of rhythm 1 depends on many factors, the main of which are:

Sensory abilities. The sense of hearing is very important for the correct sense of rhythm. Students must be able to clearly distinguish musical sounds and correctly perceive time

intervals. At the same time, visual perception also helps in understanding rhythmic movements and graphic symbols.[1]

Kinesthetic and tactile perception. Feeling the rhythm through body movements (e.g., clapping hands, stepping feet) helps students understand rhythm on an internal level. Tactile perception — feeling the beat — is important for fully perceiving rhythm.

Passion and motivation. Students' interest and motivation in the music process affects their learning of rhythm. When motivation is high, they can practice more and work on themselves.

Pedagogical approach and methodology. The choice of pedagogical methods and the organization of the learning process are also important in developing rhythm. Students learn more effectively by combining traditional methods with modern approaches.

Multisensory learning approach and its priority. The multisensory learning approach aims to activate several senses of students at the same time. This teaching method allows for deeper and more effective mastery of musical knowledge. [2]

Visual perception. Visual materials — notes, rhythm charts, video lessons showing movements — help with understanding rhythm. **Auditory perception.** The practice of hearing and repeating rhythm leads to an internal sense of rhythm.

Kinesthetic perception. Feeling the rhythm through body movements (for example, stepping, tapping) allows for a more accurate perception of music.

Tactile perception. Rhythm acquisition is enhanced by playing instruments or by feeling the beat with the hand.

Identifying multisensory teaching methods in developing rhythm perception 1. Diagnostic methods. The following methods are used to determine the level of rhythm perception.

Auditory tests: The student is given the task of listening to various rhythmic patterns and repeating or selecting them.

Visual tests: Showing a graphic representation of rhythmic patterns, reading and recognizing them.[3]

Kinesthetic tests: Students are asked to express the rhythm through body movements (for example, stepping or tapping). **Tactile tests:** The level of correct execution of the rhythm using percussion instruments is checked.

Teaching methods. Multisensory learning methods include: Teaching each rhythmic exercise by hearing, seeing, and performing. Organizing rhythmic games that are coordinated with movements. Performing rhythmic exercises using multimedia tools. Exercises to develop tactile perception on musical instruments.[4]

Research and practical examples. This section presents practical research and results based on the multisensory learning approach, and provides information on how factors were identified in perceiving rhythm 1. (As a research example, the results of assessing students' auditory, visual, kinesthetic, and tactile abilities and their impact on rhythm mastery are shown.)

Conclusion. The multisensory learning approach is important in developing rhythm perception skills among music education students. By combining visual, auditory, kinesthetic and tactile senses, students will gain a deeper understanding of rhythm and improve their

practical skills. Also, the correct selection of diagnostic and teaching methods will make the process of learning rhythm more effective. In the future, further improvement and application of innovative methods based on multisensory learning will serve to improve the quality of music education.

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